

cap on, then is fixed to the tiller site by means of a tape and pole. The cap is then removed. A thermometer is fixed similarly. Any number of such bottles and thermometers can be kept at vantage points to get an average estimate of the humidity and temperature at a given area. The bottles are stoppered and reweighed after specific time periods. The difference in weights is the actual amount of moisture absorbed from that environment.

The technique has been used in measuring the temperature and moisture levels in the area surrounding a crop of HR12 (a tall, low-tillering variety) and IET1444 (a semidwarf, high-tillering variety).

Microclimate in tall (HR12) and semidwarf (IET1444) rice varieties. AICRIP, Hyderabad, India.

	Av temperature (°C)		Av atmospheric humidity (g)	
	Near outer tillers	Near inner tillers	Near outer tillers	Near inner tillers
<i>HR12</i>				
Around plot	32.58	31.25	0.020	0.025
Within plot	30.92	29.75	0.023	0.032
<i>IET1444</i>				
Around plot	31.00	29.83	0.020	0.023
Within plot	29.92	28.83	0.020	0.024

Trend in temperature and humidity fluctuations (variety: IET4141), Hyderabad, India.

ity). Statistically the data were highly significant (see table).

The figure shows the temperature and moisture levels of another semidwarf, IET4141, recorded over a 2-day period.

The method is simple and useful in categorizing the moisture-temperature relationships in restricted areas within a

plant canopy to explain pest buildup. Further studies on the relationship between microclimate and the buildup of brown planthoppers and fungal pathogens in high-tillering semidwarf varieties with dense canopies are under way. ■

Effect of low temperature and low light intensity on the heading stage and flowering of indica rice

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Rice plants in southern China are sometimes damaged at the heading stage by low temperature and low light intensity in autumn. Thus, the sterility of late-season rice varieties caused by cold temperature can be an important constraint to rice production.

We examined the effect of cold temperature and low light on the physiological characters of rice anthers and flowers, and on the distribution or assimilation of ¹⁴C and ³²P in rice organs. Our objective was to identify

agronomic practices that prevent cold injury in rice cultivation.

A low night temperature of 12° C and a high day temperature of 22° C were maintained in artificial light cabinets. Light intensity was maintained at about 2,000 lx and relative humidity from 71 to 83%.

The respiratory intensity of rice plant florets decreased by 7.5% and that of anthers decreased by 25% after 24 hours of cold temperature and low light treatment. It decreased by 36.1% and 81.2% in the 48-hour treatment, and by 30.6% and 75.0% in the 106-hour treatment. Thus, prolongation of cold temperature and low light intensity seriously damaged the anthers.

In the first experiment with ¹⁴C (Table 1) the ¹⁴C values (counts per minute [cpm]/50 mg) and the total ¹⁴C values

differed markedly. The control flag leaf contained 4,497 cpm/ 50 mg and a total of 18,263 cpm; the treated flag leaf had 6,309 cpm/ 50 mg and a total of 23,953 cpm. Cold temperature and low light impeded the translocation of photosynthetic products of ¹⁴C from the flag leaf to the other organs and decreased their exported percentage. But the total ¹⁴C content (1 29,697 cpm) of treated plants was less than that of the control plants (377,471 cpm). The total ¹⁴C contents decreased in organs other than the flag leaf. In treated roots, it decreased even more (treated roots, 44 cpm/ 50 mg and 712 total cpm; control roots, 9,999 cpm/ 50 mg and 157,369 total cpm). Thus the roots injured by cold temperature and low light were famished and received less energy. On the other hand, cold temperature and low light

Table 1. Effect of cold temperature and low light on the export and distribution of photosynthetic products of ^{14}C (^{14}C supplied before treatment with cold temperature and low light). Guangzhou, China.

Organ	^{14}C content					
	Control ^a (natural condition)			Treated ^a with cold temp and low light		
	cpm/50 mg	Total cpm	%	cpm/50 mg	Total cpm	%
Flag leaf	4,497 ± 637	18,263	4.8	6,039 ± 795	23,953	1.8
Flag leaf sheath	2,091 ± 402	13,327	3.5	1,636 ± 346	8,630	6.6
Functional leaf blade	1,039 ± 934	10,993	2.9	20 ± 11	197	0.2
Functional leaf sheath	954 ± 303	9,571	2.5	32 ± 12	292	0.2
Panicle	5,703 ± 1,299	99,118	26.3	4,358 ± 2,113	52,304	40.3
Stem	3,490 ± 1,716	68,830	18.2	2,540 ± 1,040	43,609	33.6
Root	9,999 ± 4,216	157,369	41.7	44 ± 1.5	712	0.6
Total cpm in rice plant		377,471	100		129,697	100

^acpm = counts per minute (radioactive isotope intensity).

decreased the root's activities and photosynthetic products. From these results, we can deduce that the root is damaged more seriously than the other organs

are.

The total ^{32}P content and the content per 50 mg in each organ affected by cold temperature and low light, except the

Table 2. Effect of cold temperature and low light on the absorption and distribution of ^{32}P in the rice plant. Guangzhou, China.

Organ	^{32}P (com/50 mg)	
	Control (natural conditions)	Treated with cold temp and low light
Leaf blade	438 ± 33	434 ± 49
Leaf sheath	399 ± 31	428 ± 103
Stem	365 ± 21	361 ± 61
Panicle	436 ± 61	138 ± 6

panicle, were almost the same as those in the control organs (Table 2). The ^{32}P content in the treated panicles was 31.6% that in the control panicles, which indicates that cold temperature and low light impeded the translocation of ^{32}P from roots to panicles. That illustrates that cold temperature and low light can greatly harm panicle growth. ■

Measuring the tensile strength of japonica-indica hybrid rices in Korea

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In Korea, about 76% of the paddy fields are planted to japonica-indica hybrid rices.

The rice spikelet's tensile strength at harvest was measured in japonica-indica hybrid rices and compared with that in japonica rices. The abscission layer between the pedicel and the rachilla of the spikelet also was studied.

The japonica-indica rices generally had lower tensile strength than the japonica rices (see table). Yushin had the lowest tensile strength (98 g), and Milyang 21 had the highest (188 g). However, Milyang 21 had lower strength than Nongbeak, which had the lowest value among the japonica recommended rice varieties. Akibare had the highest tensile strength among the japonica-type rices tested.

In the japonica-indica varieties Yushin and Milyang 21, the parenchymatous cells of the abscission layer, which extends from the epidermis to near the central vascular tissue in the pedicel, collapsed (see figure). In the japonica Jojeongjo, however, the parenchymatous cells did not collapse and in Akibare, also a japonica, the abscission

Degree of grain shedding of the recommended rice varieties in Korea.

Variety	Tensile strength (g) ± S.D.
<i>Japonica-indica hybrid rice</i>	
Yushin	98 ± 32.9
Suwon 258	100 ± 29.0
Suwon 251	107 ± 33.8
Milyang 23	119 ± 36.0
Nopoong	131 ± 38.5
Joseng tongil	133 ± 34.1
Rekyeong	134 ± 35.4
Tongil-chal	142 ± 35.4
Yeongnamjoseng	147 ± 34.6
Iri 326	156 ± 33.0
Milyang 30	165 ± 38.2
Suwon 264	183 ± 38.6
Milyang 21	188 ± 30.7
<i>Japonica rice</i>	
Nongbeak	195 ± 32.7
Satominori	226 ± 43.9
Palkeum	237 ± 47.9
Akibare	245 ± 42.9
Jinheung	245 ± 51.0
Jojeongjo ^a	94 ± 34.0

^aLocal variety in old time.

layer could not be found.

The results show that the abscission layer of the japonica-indica hybrid rices in Korea is the same as that of indica rice. ■

Micrographs of longitudinal sections of the abscission layer in Yushin (top), Milyang 21 (second), Jojeongjo (third), and Akibare (bottom). Note the difference in collapse of the cells of the abscission layer (A). V = vascular tissue.

